

THE ROLE OF PSYCHOLOGY IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract: *In this article, I want to share my experience and thoughts about how psychology plays an important role in teaching English. During my teaching practice, I learned that understanding students' emotions, motivation, and learning styles can help teachers to teach better. I also explain how I tried to make all students feel involved and respected in class.*

Keywords: *Psychology, English teaching, motivation, student confidence, classroom atmosphere, learning styles.*

Teaching English is not only about grammar and vocabulary. It is also about understanding students' minds and feelings. Every student is different. Some are active, some are shy. Some like speaking, some prefer writing. As a future teacher, I realized that psychology helps me to connect with students better. If we understand their needs and emotions, we can make the lessons more interesting and useful for them. Psychological Aspects in Language Teaching

Motivation is very important in language learning. If students are interested, they learn faster. I always try to make my lessons fun and active. For example, I use games, group work, and competitions. One activity my students liked was "Word Race" – a fun game to learn new words. I saw that when students enjoy the lesson, they want to learn more even outside the classroom.

Self-confidence and anxiety

Many students are afraid to speak English because they think they will make mistakes. I saw this problem during my practice. To solve it, I used pair work. First, students practiced speaking with a partner, then they spoke in front of the class. This helped reduce fear and improved their confidence. Classroom atmosphere and emotions. If the classroom has a friendly and warm atmosphere, students feel safe and happy. I often start the lesson by asking, "How do you feel today?" It helps students relax and open up. When students feel that their teacher cares, they are more active and positive in class. Memory and learning styles Students have different ways of learning. Some learn by listening, others by seeing or writing. That's why I use colorful flashcards, pictures, videos, and listening tasks in my lessons. I try to mix different methods to help every student remember new words and grammar better. My Practice and Observations. During my teaching practice at School No. 8 in Bukhara district, I worked with students of different characters. Some were fast learners, some needed more time. I tried to make sure that no student felt ignored or left behind. I gave attention to every student and encouraged them all. I also noticed that some students were quiet but very smart. I gave them special tasks to show their talents. One example was during the topic "Movie Genres." I asked students to draw posters of their favorite movies and present them in class. They loved it! I saw their creative sides and how happy they were to speak in English. This activity helped me understand how important it is to know students' psychology and interests.

Conclusion. From my experience, I understood that a good English teacher should also be a bit of a psychologist. We should see not only the mistakes but also the emotions of our students. When we teach with heart, care, and understanding, students feel it. Psychology helps us create better lessons and stronger connections with learners. Every student is unique, and it is our job to help each one of them grow.

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